

CARDIOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY OF HYDRO-ETHANOLIC EXTRACT OF CUMINUM CYMINUM SEEDS AGAINST ISOPRENALINE- AND DOXORUBICIN-INDUCED CARDIOTOXICITY IN RATS

Murali Kumar K, *Sanketh T

Viratnagar Main Road, Bommanahalli Bengaluru Karnataka India.

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*Corresponding Author

Sanketh T

Viratnagar Main Road,
Bommanahalli Bengaluru Karnataka
India.

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The present study aimed to evaluate the cardioprotective potential of the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* seeds against experimentally induced cardiotoxicity in rats. **Materials and Methods:** Seeds of *Cuminum cyminum* were shade-dried, powdered, and extracted using ethanol: water (70:30) in a Soxhlet apparatus. Preliminary phytochemical screening was performed, and the extract was standardized by determining total phenolic and total flavonoid content. In vitro antioxidant activity was assessed using DPPH and nitric oxide scavenging assays. Acute oral toxicity was conducted according to OECD guideline 423. For in vivo studies, cardiotoxicity was induced using doxorubicin (10 mg/kg, i.v.) and isoprenaline (85 mg/kg, s.c.). Rats were pretreated with hydro-ethanolic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* (HECC) at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg, p.o., and ascorbic acid

(20 mg/kg, p.o.) as standard. Serum biochemical markers including CK-MB, LDH, SGOT, SGPT, total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), total protein (TP), HDL, and LDL were estimated. Cardiac tissue homogenates were analyzed for reduced glutathione (GSH) and lipid peroxidation (LPO). Histopathological examination of myocardial tissue was performed. **Results:** The extract showed no mortality up to 2000 mg/kg in acute toxicity studies. HECC pretreatment significantly reduced serum cardiac biomarkers (CK-MB, LDH, SGOT, SGPT, TC, TG) and increased HDL levels compared to cardiotoxic control groups. Antioxidant

analysis revealed a significant increase in GSH levels and a decrease in LPO levels. Histopathological evaluation demonstrated near-normal myocardial architecture in HECC-treated groups, particularly at 400 mg/kg, comparable to ascorbic acid. **Conclusion:** The hydro-ethanolic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* seeds exhibited significant dose-dependent cardioprotective activity against isoprenaline- and doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity in rats. The protective effect may be attributed to its phytoconstituents, including phenolics and flavonoids, and its potent antioxidant properties.

KEYWORDS: *Cuminum cyminum*, cardioprotection, isoprenaline, doxorubicin, antioxidant, glutathione, lipid peroxidation.

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of mortality worldwide, accounting for approximately 17.9 million deaths annually. Ischemic heart disease and stroke contribute to more than 80% of total CVD-related deaths. In India, CVDs account for nearly one-quarter of total mortality, with a rapidly increasing prevalence attributed to urbanization, sedentary lifestyle, unhealthy dietary habits, obesity, diabetes, hypertension, and hyperlipidemia.

Oxidative stress plays a central role in the pathogenesis of cardiovascular disorders. Excessive generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) leads to lipid peroxidation, endothelial dysfunction, mitochondrial damage, and myocardial injury. Atherosclerosis, the primary underlying cause of most cardiovascular complications, is closely associated with hyperlipidemia and oxidative modification of low-density lipoproteins (LDL). Rupture of atherosclerotic plaques ultimately precipitates myocardial infarction and stroke.

Certain chemotherapeutic and pharmacological agents are also known to induce cardiotoxicity through oxidative mechanisms. Doxorubicin, a widely used anthracycline anticancer agent, is highly effective against solid tumors, leukemias, and breast cancer; however, its clinical utility is limited by dose-dependent cardiotoxicity. The proposed mechanisms include free radical generation, lipid peroxidation, mitochondrial dysfunction, and apoptosis of cardiomyocytes.

Similarly, Isoprenaline (isoproterenol), a synthetic β -adrenergic agonist, induces myocardial stress, infarct-like necrosis, and oxidative damage in experimental models. It is commonly

used to study cardiotoxicity due to its ability to generate free radicals, increase lipid peroxidation, and elevate circulating lipoproteins.

Although several synthetic drugs such as statins and fibrates are available for the management of cardiovascular disorders, their long-term use may be associated with adverse drug reactions and drug–drug interactions. This has led to growing interest in herbal and dietary interventions with cardioprotective potential and better safety profiles.

Spices used in traditional diets are increasingly recognized for their pharmacological properties, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hypolipidemic, and antihypertensive effects. Among them, *Cuminum cyminum* (cumin), commonly known as jeera, is widely used in culinary and traditional medicine systems such as Ayurveda. It has been reported to possess antihyperglycemic, antihyperlipidemic, antiplatelet, and antioxidant activities. Phytochemical investigations have revealed the presence of essential oils, terpenoids, phenolic compounds, and flavonoids, which may contribute to its biological effects.

However, limited scientific evidence is available regarding its role in preventing drug-induced cardiotoxicity and myocardial injury.

Therefore, the present study was designed to evaluate the cardioprotective effect of the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* seeds against doxorubicin- and isoprenaline-induced cardiotoxicity in experimental rats, with particular emphasis on biochemical, antioxidant, and histopathological parameters.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material and Extraction

Dried seeds of *Cuminum cyminum* were procured from a local supplier in Bengaluru, India, and authenticated by the Regional Ayurveda Research Institute for Metabolic Disorders (RARIMD), Bengaluru. The seeds were cleaned, shade-dried, coarsely powdered, and stored in airtight containers.

The hydro-ethanolic extract was prepared using a Soxhlet apparatus with ethanol:water (70:30 v/v). The extract was concentrated to semisolid consistency, stored in airtight glass containers, and preserved at 4°C until further use. The extract was designated as HECC (Hydro-ethanolic Extract of *Cuminum cyminum*).

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Qualitative phytochemical screening of HECC was performed using standard procedures to detect the presence of carbohydrates, alkaloids, glycosides, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, steroids, and triterpenoids.

Determination of Total Phenolic and Flavonoid Content

Total Phenolic Content (TPC)

TPC was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu method. Absorbance was measured at 765 nm using a UV–visible spectrophotometer. Gallic acid was used as the reference standard, and results were expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE)/g of extract.

Total Flavonoid Content (TFC)

TFC was estimated by the aluminum chloride colorimetric method. Absorbance was recorded at 510 nm. Rutin was used as the standard, and results were expressed as mg rutin equivalents/g dry extract.

In Vitro Antioxidant Activity

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

Free radical scavenging activity was evaluated using the DPPH assay. Various concentrations of HECC (5–25 µg/mL) were incubated with DPPH solution, and absorbance was measured at 517 nm after 30 minutes. Ascorbic acid served as the reference standard. Percentage inhibition was calculated, and IC₅₀ values were determined.

Nitric Oxide Scavenging Assay

Nitric oxide radicals were generated from sodium nitroprusside and quantified using Griess reagent. Absorbance was measured at 546 nm, and percentage inhibition was calculated relative to control.

Experimental Animals

Female albino mice (20–25 g) were used for acute toxicity studies. Wistar rats (150–250 g) of either sex were used for cardioprotective evaluation.

Animals were housed under standard laboratory conditions (12 h light/dark cycle, controlled temperature) with free access to standard pellet diet and water. All experimental procedures were conducted in accordance with CPCSEA guidelines and were approved by the

Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC), Government College of Pharmacy, Bengaluru (Approval No: GCP/IAEC/DOP/20/E.C/ADM/2020-21/36; dated 29/08/2020).

Acute Oral Toxicity Study

Acute toxicity was evaluated according to OECD guideline 423. HECC was administered orally at 2000 mg/kg to female mice. Animals were observed for 48 hours for signs of toxicity and mortality. No mortality was observed; therefore, 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg (1/10th and 1/5th of the maximum dose) were selected for further studies.

Experimental Design

Model I: Doxorubicin-Induced Cardiotoxicity

Cardiotoxicity was induced using Doxorubicin (10 mg/kg, i.p.). HECC (200 and 400 mg/kg, p.o.) and ascorbic acid (20 mg/kg, p.o.) were administered for 18 days prior to doxorubicin injection.

Animal Grouping (n = 6 per group)

- **Group I:** Normal control (saline)
- **Group II:** Doxorubicin control
- **Group III:** Ascorbic acid + Doxorubicin
- **Group IV:** HECC 200 mg/kg + Doxorubicin
- **Group V:** HECC 400 mg/kg + Doxorubicin

Blood samples were collected 48 h after DOX administration for biochemical analysis. Hearts were excised for antioxidant assays and histopathology.

Model II: Isoprenaline-Induced Cardiotoxicity

Cardiotoxicity was induced using Isoprenaline (85 mg/kg, s.c.) administered for two consecutive days. HECC was administered orally for 14 days prior to isoprenaline challenge.

Animal Grouping (n = 6 per group)

- **Group I:** Normal control
- **Group II:** Isoprenaline control
- **Group III:** Ascorbic acid + Isoprenaline
- **Group IV:** HECC 200 mg/kg + Isoprenaline
- **Group V:** HECC 400 mg/kg + Isoprenaline

After 48 hours, blood and heart tissues were collected for analysis.

Biochemical Estimations

Serum samples were analyzed for

- Creatine kinase-MB (CK-MB)
- Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH)
- Aspartate aminotransferase (AST/SGOT)
- Alanine aminotransferase (ALT/SGPT)
- Total cholesterol (TC)
- Triglycerides (TG)
- Total protein (TP)

Commercial diagnostic kits and semi-auto/auto analyzers were used following manufacturer protocols.

Estimation of Tissue Antioxidant Parameters

Reduced Glutathione (GSH)

GSH levels in heart homogenates were estimated using Ellman's reagent (DTNB) and measured at 412 nm. Results were expressed as $\mu\text{mol/mg}$ protein.

Lipid Peroxidation (LPO)

LPO was assessed by measuring malondialdehyde (MDA) levels using the thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) method at 532 nm. Results were expressed as nmol MDA/mg protein.

Histopathological Examination

Heart tissues were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin, embedded in paraffin, sectioned, and stained with hematoxylin and eosin. Sections were examined under a light microscope for myocardial necrosis, inflammatory infiltration, and structural alterations.

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM ($n = 6$). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test (GraphPad Prism v6.0). A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Phytochemical Evaluation of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Cuminum cyminum* (HECC)

Extractive Yield and Organoleptic Properties

The hydroalcoholic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* seeds was prepared using Soxhlet extraction with ethanol:water (7:3). The extract was dark brown in color and semisolid in consistency. The percentage yield was found to be **8.72% w/w**.

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Qualitative phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of:

- Carbohydrates
- Alkaloids (positive in Dragendorff's test)
- Phenolic compounds and tannins
- Flavonoids
- Steroids and terpenoids
- Essential oils

Glycosides were absent. The extract showed positive results for Liebermann–Burchard, Salkowski, Shinoda, ferric chloride, and Sudan III tests, confirming the presence of bioactive secondary metabolites.

Total Phenolic Content

The total phenolic content of HECC was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu method and expressed as gallic acid equivalents (GAE).

The total phenolic content was found to be

4.749 ± 0.1103 mg GAE/g of extract

Total Flavonoid Content

The total flavonoid content was estimated using the aluminum chloride colorimetric method and expressed as rutin equivalents.

The total flavonoid content was

52.55 ± 0.7186 mg rutin equivalents/g dry weight

In Vitro Antioxidant Activity

DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity

HECC exhibited concentration-dependent DPPH radical scavenging activity.

- IC₅₀ of Ascorbic acid: **34.19 µg/mL**
- IC₅₀ of HECC: **44.33 µg/mL**

Although the extract showed slightly lower activity than ascorbic acid, significant antioxidant potential was observed.

Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Activity

The nitric oxide scavenging activity of HECC also showed dose-dependent inhibition.

- IC₅₀ of Ascorbic acid: **16.66 µg/mL**
- IC₅₀ of HECC: **40.92 µg/mL**

The extract demonstrated moderate nitric oxide scavenging capacity compared to the standard.

Pharmacological Evaluation

Acute Toxicity Study

Acute oral toxicity was conducted according to OECD guideline 423. No mortality or toxic signs were observed at 2000 mg/kg. Therefore, doses of:

- 200 mg/kg (1/10th)
- 400 mg/kg (1/5th)

were selected for further pharmacological studies.

Doxorubicin-Induced Cardiotoxicity Model

General Observations

Rats treated with doxorubicin exhibited

- Scruffy fur
- Pink tinge
- Red exudates around eyes and nose
- Soft watery feces
- Enlarged abdomen

Pretreatment with HECC (200 and 400 mg/kg) and ascorbic acid markedly attenuated these symptoms.

Heart Weight

Doxorubicin significantly increased heart weight compared to normal control ($p < 0.001$).

Pretreatment with HECC (400 mg/kg) significantly reduced heart weight toward normal levels.

Group	Heart Weight (g)
Normal	0.8923 ± 0.0234
DOX	1.207 ± 0.0497
Ascorbic acid	0.9213 ± 0.0287
HECC 200 mg/kg	1.1455 ± 0.0388
HECC 400 mg/kg	0.9987 ± 0.0265

Serum Cardiac Biomarkers

Doxorubicin significantly elevated serum markers including:

- AST (SGOT)
- ALT (SGPT)
- CK-MB
- LDH
- Total cholesterol
- Triglycerides

Pretreatment with HECC (especially 400 mg/kg) significantly reduced these parameters compared to DOX group ($p < 0.05$ – 0.001).

The high-dose HECC group demonstrated greater cardioprotection than the low-dose group.

Endogenous Antioxidant Parameters

Reduced Glutathione (GSH)

DOX significantly decreased GSH levels ($p < 0.001$).

HECC treatment significantly restored GSH levels in a dose-dependent manner.

Lipid Peroxidation (LPO)

DOX markedly increased TBARS levels indicating lipid peroxidation.

HECC (200 and 400 mg/kg) significantly reduced LPO levels compared to DOX group ($p < 0.001$).

Histopathological Findings (DOX Model)

- **Normal control:** Normal myocardial architecture.

- **DOX group:** Myocardial degeneration, inflammatory infiltration, fibrosis, congestion, and edema.
- **Ascorbic acid:** Near normal architecture.
- **HECC 200 mg/kg:** Mild degeneration and focal inflammation.
- **HECC 400 mg/kg:** Near normal myocardial structure with minimal pathological alterations.

Isoprenaline-Induced Cardiotoxicity Model

Similar cardioprotective effects were observed in the isoprenaline model.

HECC significantly

- Reduced heart weight
- Lowered serum cardiac enzymes
- Decreased lipid peroxidation
- Increased GSH levels
- Improved histological architecture

The high dose (400 mg/kg) showed effects comparable to ascorbic acid.

Statistical Analysis

All data are expressed as Mean \pm SEM (n = 6). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Summary of Key Findings

- HECC contains phenolics and flavonoids.
- Exhibits significant in vitro antioxidant activity.
- Provides dose-dependent cardioprotection.
- Reduces oxidative stress markers.
- Restores endogenous antioxidants.
- Improves histopathological damage.
- High dose (400 mg/kg) shows stronger effect.

RESULTS

Phytochemical Characterization of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Cuminum cyminum* (HECC)

Extractive Yield and Physical Characteristics

The hydroalcoholic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* seeds was prepared using Soxhlet extraction with ethanol:water (7:3 v/v). The extract was dark brown, semisolid in consistency, and yielded 8.72% w/w of dried extract.

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Qualitative phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of carbohydrates, alkaloids (positive Dragendorff's test), phenolic compounds, tannins, flavonoids, steroids, terpenoids, and essential oils. Glycosides were absent. Positive reactions in Liebermann–Burchard, Salkowski, Shinoda, ferric chloride, and Sudan III tests confirmed the presence of bioactive secondary metabolites.

Total Phenolic Content

The total phenolic content (TPC), estimated using the Folin–Ciocalteu method and expressed as gallic acid equivalents (GAE), was

4.749 ± 0.1103 mg GAE/g of extract

Total Flavonoid Content

The total flavonoid content (TFC), determined by the aluminum chloride colorimetric method and expressed as rutin equivalents, was

52.55 ± 0.7186 mg rutin equivalents/g dry weight

In Vitro Antioxidant Activity

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

HECC exhibited concentration-dependent DPPH radical scavenging activity. The IC₅₀ value of HECC was 44.33 µg/mL compared with 34.19 µg/mL for ascorbic acid, indicating moderate antioxidant activity relative to the standard.

Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay

HECC demonstrated dose-dependent nitric oxide scavenging activity with an IC₅₀ value of 40.92 µg/mL, compared to 16.66 µg/mL for ascorbic acid, suggesting appreciable free radical neutralizing capacity.

Acute Toxicity Study

Acute oral toxicity was evaluated according to OECD guideline 423. No mortality or observable signs of toxicity were recorded at 2000 mg/kg. Accordingly, 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg were selected as experimental doses for subsequent pharmacological investigations.

Effect of HECC on Doxorubicin-Induced Cardiotoxicity

General Observations

Animals treated with doxorubicin exhibited clinical signs of toxicity including scruffy fur, pinkish discoloration, periocular and nasal exudates, diarrhea, and abdominal enlargement. These symptoms were markedly attenuated in animals pretreated with HECC (200 and 400 mg/kg) and ascorbic acid.

Heart Weight

Doxorubicin administration resulted in a significant increase in heart weight compared to the normal control group ($p < 0.001$). Pretreatment with HECC (400 mg/kg) significantly reduced heart weight toward normal levels.

Group	Heart Weight (g)
Normal control	0.8923 ± 0.0234
Doxorubicin	1.207 ± 0.0497
Ascorbic acid	0.9213 ± 0.0287
HECC 200 mg/kg	1.1455 ± 0.0388
HECC 400 mg/kg	0.9987 ± 0.0265

Serum Cardiac Biomarkers

Doxorubicin significantly elevated serum AST (SGOT), ALT (SGPT), CK-MB, LDH, total cholesterol, and triglycerides ($p < 0.001$ vs normal control).

Pretreatment with HECC significantly attenuated these elevations in a dose-dependent manner ($p < 0.05$ – 0.001 vs DOX group), with the 400 mg/kg dose showing greater protective efficacy.

Endogenous Antioxidant Status

Reduced Glutathione (GSH)

Doxorubicin significantly decreased cardiac GSH levels compared with normal control ($p < 0.001$). HECC pretreatment significantly restored GSH levels in a dose-dependent manner.

Lipid Peroxidation (LPO)

Doxorubicin significantly increased TBARS levels, indicating enhanced lipid peroxidation ($p < 0.001$). HECC pretreatment significantly reduced LPO levels compared with DOX-treated animals ($p < 0.001$).

Histopathological Findings (DOX Model)

- **Normal control:** Preserved myocardial architecture without pathological alterations.
- **Doxorubicin group:** Myocardial degeneration, inflammatory cell infiltration, fibrosis, congestion, and interstitial edema.
- **Ascorbic acid group:** Near-normal myocardial structure.
- **HECC 200 mg/kg:** Mild myocardial degeneration with focal inflammation.
- **HECC 400 mg/kg:** Markedly preserved myocardial architecture with minimal pathological changes.

Effect of HECC on Isoprenaline-Induced Cardiotoxicity

In the isoprenaline model, HECC produced similar cardioprotective effects.

Isoprenaline significantly increased heart weight and serum cardiac biomarkers while reducing antioxidant status ($p < 0.001$ vs normal control). Pretreatment with HECC significantly

- Reduced heart weight
- Decreased AST, ALT, CK-MB, LDH, TC, and TG levels
- Increased GSH levels
- Decreased lipid peroxidation
- Improved histopathological alterations

The high-dose group (400 mg/kg) demonstrated effects comparable to ascorbic acid.

Statistical Analysis

All results are expressed as Mean \pm SEM ($n = 6$). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Overall Findings

HECC demonstrated

- Significant antioxidant activity in vitro

- Dose-dependent cardioprotective activity
- Reduction of oxidative stress markers
- Restoration of endogenous antioxidants
- Improvement in biochemical and histopathological parameters

The 400 mg/kg dose exhibited superior cardioprotective efficacy.

DISCUSSION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) remain a leading cause of global morbidity and mortality. Although pharmacological agents such as β -blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, calcium channel blockers, statins, fibrates, and antiplatelet agents are widely used in clinical practice, their long-term use is often associated with adverse drug reactions and drug–drug interactions. Consequently, there has been increasing interest in identifying safer cardioprotective agents from natural sources. Medicinal plants rich in bioactive phytoconstituents have emerged as promising alternatives due to their antioxidant and lipid-modulating properties.

Cuminum cyminum (white cumin), traditionally used as a culinary spice, has been reported to possess antioxidant, antihyperlipidemic, hypotensive, and blood-purifying properties. However, its cardioprotective potential against drug-induced myocardial injury has not been extensively investigated. The present study was therefore designed to evaluate the cardioprotective activity of the hydroalcoholic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* (HECC) using doxorubicin- and isoprenaline-induced cardiotoxicity models in rats.

Phytochemical Basis of Cardioprotection

The hydroalcoholic extract yielded 8.78% w/w and was standardized based on total phenolic and flavonoid contents. HECC exhibited appreciable levels of phenolics (4.79 ± 0.1103 mg GAE/g) and flavonoids (52.55 ± 0.7186 mg rutin equivalents/g), indicating the presence of potent antioxidant constituents.

Phenolic compounds and flavonoids are well documented for their free radical scavenging and membrane-stabilizing properties. The *in vitro* antioxidant assays demonstrated that HECC possessed significant DPPH and nitric oxide radical scavenging activity, supporting its potential to counteract oxidative stress. Although the activity was slightly lower than ascorbic acid, the extract exhibited biologically relevant antioxidant capacity.

Oxidative stress plays a critical role in the pathogenesis of cardiotoxicity, particularly in anthracycline-induced myocardial injury. Therefore, the observed antioxidant activity of HECC provided a strong mechanistic rationale for its *in vivo* evaluation.

Effect of HECC in Doxorubicin-Induced Cardiotoxicity

Doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity is primarily mediated by excessive generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), mitochondrial dysfunction, lipid peroxidation, and depletion of endogenous antioxidant systems. In the present study, doxorubicin administration significantly elevated serum cardiac biomarkers (AST, ALT, CK-MB, LDH), lipid parameters (TC, TG), and total protein levels, confirming myocardial damage.

Additionally, doxorubicin markedly reduced myocardial glutathione (GSH) levels and increased lipid peroxidation (LPO), indicating oxidative stress-mediated injury. These findings are consistent with previously reported mechanisms involving ROS generation, mitochondrial impairment, Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase dysfunction, and adrenergic dysregulation.

Pretreatment with HECC significantly attenuated the elevation of serum biomarkers and restored antioxidant status in a dose-dependent manner. The high dose (400 mg/kg) demonstrated greater protective efficacy, although ascorbic acid showed comparatively stronger cardioprotection.

The restoration of GSH levels and reduction in lipid peroxidation suggest that HECC mitigates doxorubicin-induced myocardial injury primarily through antioxidant mechanisms. Histopathological findings further corroborated the biochemical data, as HECC-treated groups exhibited preservation of myocardial architecture with reduced inflammation and fibrosis.

Effect of HECC in Isoprenaline-Induced Cardiotoxicity

Isoprenaline, a β_1 -adrenergic agonist, induces myocardial injury by increasing heart rate and contractility, leading to an imbalance between oxygen supply and demand. High-dose isoprenaline (85 mg/kg) is known to produce myocardial necrosis through oxidative stress, enhanced phospholipase activity, adenylyl cyclase stimulation, and excessive free radical generation.

In the present study, isoprenaline significantly elevated serum cardiac markers and lipid parameters while reducing GSH levels and increasing lipid peroxidation. These alterations confirm severe myocardial oxidative damage.

Pretreatment with HECC significantly reversed these changes in a dose-dependent manner. The extract normalized serum biomarkers, reduced lipid peroxidation, restored endogenous antioxidant levels, and improved histological features of cardiac tissue. These findings strongly indicate that HECC exerts protective effects against β -adrenergic stress-induced myocardial injury.

Role of Antioxidant and Antihyperlipidemic Effects

Elevated lipid levels are recognized risk factors in cardiovascular pathology. HECC significantly reduced triglyceride and total cholesterol levels in both experimental models. The antihyperlipidemic activity of *Cuminum cyminum* may contribute to its overall cardioprotective effect by reducing lipid accumulation and oxidative modification, thereby exerting anti-atherosclerotic potential.

The cardioprotective activity observed in this study can therefore be attributed to

1. Free radical scavenging activity
2. Restoration of endogenous antioxidant defense systems
3. Inhibition of lipid peroxidation
4. Improvement in lipid profile
5. Preservation of myocardial structural integrity

These effects are likely mediated by the presence of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, terpenoids, and essential oils in the extract.

Proposed Mechanism

Based on the findings, oxidative stress appears to be the rate-limiting step in both doxorubicin- and isoprenaline-induced cardiotoxicity. HECC may exert cardioprotection primarily by interrupting ROS generation, preventing oxidative damage to cellular membranes, and stabilizing myocardial antioxidant defense systems.

CONCLUSION OF DISCUSSION

The present findings demonstrate that hydroalcoholic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* confers significant, dose-dependent cardioprotection against chemically induced myocardial injury.

The protective effect is largely attributable to its antioxidant and antihyperlipidemic properties. Further studies exploring molecular pathways and clinical relevance are warranted.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Aim

The present study was designed to investigate the pharmacognostic characteristics and evaluate the cardioprotective potential of the hydroalcoholic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* seeds against experimentally induced cardiotoxicity in rodents.

Specific Objectives

1. Pharmacognostic and Phytochemical Evaluation

- To collect and authenticate seeds of *Cuminum cyminum*.
- To prepare a hydroalcoholic extract (ethanol:water, 7:3) using Soxhlet extraction.
- To perform preliminary phytochemical screening of the hydroalcoholic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* (HECC).
- To quantify total phenolic and total flavonoid contents of HECC.
- To evaluate in vitro antioxidant activity of HECC using DPPH and nitric oxide radical scavenging assays.

2. Pharmacological Evaluation

- To assess the acute oral toxicity of HECC in rodents according to OECD guideline 423.
- To evaluate the cardioprotective activity of HECC against doxorubicin- and isoprenaline-induced cardiotoxicity in rats.
- To determine serum cardiac biomarkers including CK-MB, AST (SGOT), ALT (SGPT), LDH, total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), and total protein (TP).
- To assess myocardial antioxidant status by estimating reduced glutathione (GSH) and lipid peroxidation (LPO) levels in cardiac tissue.
- To perform histopathological examination of cardiac tissue to confirm biochemical findings.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates that the hydroalcoholic extract of *Cuminum cyminum* seeds (HECC) is rich in bioactive phytoconstituents, including phenolic compounds, flavonoids, terpenoids, and essential oils. Quantitative analysis confirmed appreciable levels of total

phenolics (4.749 ± 0.1103 mg GAE/g extract) and total flavonoids (52.55 ± 0.7186 mg rutin equivalents/g), which likely contribute to its biological activity.

HECC exhibited significant in vitro antioxidant activity, as evidenced by DPPH and nitric oxide radical scavenging assays. Furthermore, in vivo studies demonstrated that HECC provides significant, dose-dependent cardioprotection against both doxorubicin- and isoprenaline-induced cardiotoxicity in rats. The extract effectively attenuated elevated serum cardiac biomarkers, restored endogenous antioxidant defenses, reduced lipid peroxidation, improved lipid profile parameters, and preserved myocardial histoarchitecture.

The cardioprotective effects of HECC may be primarily attributed to its antioxidant and antihyperlipidemic properties. By mitigating oxidative stress and stabilizing myocardial cellular integrity, the extract interrupts key pathological mechanisms involved in chemically induced myocardial injury.

These findings suggest that *Cuminum cyminum* possesses promising therapeutic potential as a natural cardioprotective agent. However, further investigations, including detailed mechanistic studies, isolation of active constituents, evaluation of antiplatelet activity, and clinical validation, are warranted to fully establish its cardioprotective efficacy and translational relevance.

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